

Effect of behavior on bone health

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Introduction

Bones are the base of the body because it supports all the body systems and it contains the bone marrow which is the most important component of the body, because it offers blood cell to the organs throughout the body.

Behavior of human beings affect on bones health either positively or negatively. People whom prefer to live in closed dark flats exposing their children to severe complications that may affect the bones due to inadequate level of vitamin D level in the bodies of the children of those parents whom live in dark home without direct exposure to the sun light, Further more if those children are not feed by natural lactation their

bone health may deteriorate and may have difficulties in walking due to their bones weakness.

Nowadays bones diseases increase among Sudanese children in comparison to the past decades due to wrong understanding of civilization and escaping from local habits and tradition which practiced by the previous generation of Sudanese people whom balanced between their body needs and their own environment by exposing their children to sun light directly in the home yards and by mother's milk which is the main diet to their infants, so the body of the children will grow quickly and strongly.

Breast feeding

Inadequate health education among local population enhance spreading of bones diseases, especially among those non vaccinated children, some citizens avoid to vaccinate their children, because of wrong believes about the vaccination teams, many women use artificial milk as only source of diet to their infant and according

to these behavior their children loss a lot of beneficial minerals and immunoglobulins and other important nutrients.

The bones of vaccinated rural children are stronger than those of urban children due to dependence of rural

mothers on breast feeding as main source of diet to their children and in some cases they use also goats milk as second line of diet to their babies and from the other side the urban mothers are mostly independent on breast feeding as main dietary source to their infants, further more their children may consume soft drinks which have very negative impact on their bones.

Further more rural children walk regularly to their schools in the morning and to their fathers' farms in the afternoon in comparison to less physical activities among urban children.

Rural children in the farm

Lastly we conclude that rural persons have good behavior that maintains their bones strong due to their natural dietary sources and physical activities.

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Reference

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